

TIME FOR CRITICAL SELF-EVALUATION TO ATTAIN BETTER OUTCOMES: A JOURNEY THROUGH THE PERSPECTIVE OF AWWs ON EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION PROVIDED IN AWCS IN KERALA IN LIGHT OF NEP 2020

Azra Nasreen. V

Research scholar, Department of Home Science and Centre for Research, St. Teresa's college, Ernakulam, Kerala, India. Email- azranv3us@gmail.com

Dr. Dhanya. N

Associate Professor, Department of Home Science and Centre for Research, St. Teresa's College, Kerala, India. Ernakulam, Kerala

Paper Received On: 20 NOVEMBER 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 DECEMBER 2025

Published On: 01 JANUARY 2026

Abstract

The first six years of a child's life are vital because this is when the groundwork is established for their cognitive, social, emotional, physical, motor, and psychological development. India's Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) represents one of the most extensive child development programmes in the world. The government of India introduced the ICDS in 1975 under the Ministry of Women and Child Development (MWCD) to provide holistic development to the child through Anganwadi centers (AWCs) managed by an Anganwadi worker (AWW) and helper (AWH). ICDS offers supplementary nutrition, immunization, health check-ups, referral services, nutrition & health check-ups, and preschool education. NEP (2020) mandates that quality early childhood development, care, and education should be universally available by 2030 to ensure all children are prepared for Grade One. In Kerala, AWWs are so overburdened that the education component does not receive ample attention, or they do not get enough time for the same. In Kerala, the early childhood education component is good, but AWWs have no time to implement the same as prescribed in the curriculum due to other duties and other reasons. To understand the early childhood education in AWCs in Kerala from the perspective of AWWs and its poorly executed implementation, the present study was initiated to study the need for better change in early childhood education through AWCs in Kerala by considering NEP 2020.

Key Words: ICDS, AWCs, Early childhood education, Kerala Context, NEP 2020.

INTRODUCTION

Children are among the most delightful beings, brimming with joy, energy, and curiosity. Early exploration and learning are vital for their development. Both parents and society must offer a nurturing environment during these formative pre-school years, as development is particularly swift and profoundly influenced by the surrounding environment.

The Parliamentary Standing Committee on Education, Women, Children, Youth and Sports suggested that the WCD ministry develop a plan in collaboration with the Ministry of Education to update AWCs and enhance them as early-childhood education centers, aiming for universal ECCE access as outlined in the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. Additionally, it recommended providing timely training for AWWs to handle these new responsibilities effectively.

NEP (2020) mentioned that to achieve universal access to Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE), AWCs will be enhanced with top-notch infrastructure, play equipment, and thoroughly trained AWWs. Each AWC will feature a well-ventilated, thoughtfully designed, child-friendly, and well-constructed building, creating a stimulating and supportive learning environment. In Kerala, The Department of Women and Child Development has authorized the construction of buildings for 48 AWCs in the state under the Smart Anganwadi scheme in 2021. Along with the progression in the infrastructure of the AWCs, the advancement in the present curriculum will help in making AWCs into utilitarian early learning centers.

In Kerala, the ICDS program started as a pilot initiative in Vengara, Malappuram district, on October 2, 1975. The program has grown into a large community consisting of 33,115 AWCs across 14 districts. It serves adolescent girls, children aged 0–6 years, and pregnant and lactating women. Now, the program includes 258 ICDS projects, of which 234 are located in rural areas, 23 in urban areas, and 1 in a tribal area.

In Kerala, the early childhood education component of ICDS is excellent. Still, AWWs have no time to implement the same due to other duties and other reasons. So, to understand the curriculum and inefficient implementation, the present study was initiated to study the need for a change in early childhood education through AWCs in Kerala by considering NEP 2020

Objectives

- To collect opinions of AWWs about early childhood education provided through AWCs.
- To understand the need for change in early childhood education provided through AWCs.

Research design

A community-based descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out in 151 AWCs in the Ernakulam district in Kerala selected through purposive sampling from the Pallipuram, Kuzhipilly, and Edavanakkad Panchayats. The study utilised a self-designed questionnaire to collect data. The collected data were then consolidated, tabulated, and analysed using percentage, ANOVA and Chi-Square Test.

Abbreviations

AWCs- Anganwadi Centres

AWWs- Anganwadi Workers

ECE- Early Childhood Education

RESULTS

Year of starting operation of the selected AWCs

India's Integrated Child Development Services Programme (ICDS) is among the largest child development initiatives globally (Planning Commission, 2011). Launched in 1975, it aims to advance the nation's growth by focusing on developing its human resources. Prime Minister Indira Gandhi launched the ICDS programme in response to high rates of infant and maternal mortality (Planning Commission, 2011). Managed by community-based volunteers—the AWWs and the Anganwadi Helper (AWH)—at centres known as AWCs, the ICDS aims to deliver six key services: supplementary nutrition, immunization, health check-ups, referrals, pre-school education, and nutrition and health education.

Figure 1: Year of starting operation of the selected AWCs

The study showed that nearly fifty percent of AWCs started during 1975-1985, which is the period of implementation of ICDS in Kerala. In Kerala, the ICDS was introduced on October 2, 1975, starting as a pilot project in Vengara, Malappuram district. Over 40 years, the programme has evolved into an extensive network with 33,115 Anganwadis (AWCs) across 14 districts, serving children aged 0–6 years, adolescent girls, and pregnant and lactating

women. The scheme has expanded to encompass 258 ICDS projects, including 234 in rural areas, 23 in urban areas, and 1 in a tribal area.

Thirty-six per cent of the AWCs started during 2007-2017. The ICDS began as a pilot project in 33 community development blocks across 22 states and 1 Union Territory and was later expanded. Despite its significant national role and 39-year history, over 50 percent of its growth has taken place in the decade following 2005 (Planning Commission, 2013).

Educational qualifications of AWWs

Education of AWWs is crucial as they are paying stone to the growth of all domains of the future generation. A qualified early childhood educator can make magic in the lives of children.

Figure 2: Educational qualification of AWWs

The study showed that 51 per cent of the AWWs had SSLC as their qualification. Around 20 per cent of AWWs have VHSC/Higher Secondary as their qualification. Around 19 per cent of AWWs have PDC as their qualification. Four per cent of them have acquired a degree as their qualification. Only 5% of AWWs have qualifications related to early childhood education. Among the 151 AWWs, seven completed NTTC, and one qualified for the Balasevika course. Arya et al (2022) reported that 40.68 per cent of AWWs had finished high school.

Aspirations to pursue a career as an AWW

The works of AWWs are recognised for their diverse practices because of the six objectives of ICDS. The work provides a broad range of knowledge and social connections. It also involves a substantial workload.

Figure 3: Aspirations to pursue a career as an AWW

Figure 3 indicates that 81 per cent of AWWs had not aspired to be AWWs. They got into this profession by chance. The remaining 19 per cent of AWWs had the ambition to become AWWs. They have a strong desire to work with children or view it as a form of social service. Even though some of them mentioned that they were not aware of other duties of AWWs, they were not interested in this profession now.

The status of ECC Educators is often poorly defined, inadequate, and lacking in support. This is due to several issues, including dependence on the playway method, which can lead to minimal expectations and a lack of structured practices. ECCE professionals frequently receive limited training, face restricted career advancement and work in a field with insufficient research and documentation. In addition, the situation is more complicated by unclear policies and low funding. The ECCE field is notable for its broad range of practices but is plagued by disorganisation, minimal regulation, and few high-quality institutions. Within the ICDS framework, the situation is even more severe, as AWWs are often seen as volunteers and receive compensation that often falls below minimum wage standards. The excessive workload, particularly resulting from the need to duplicate efforts by maintaining both paper and digital registers, often forced AWWs to take work home, contributing to increased stress and fatigue. Moreover, many AWWs expressed feelings of being undervalued, especially when parents misunderstood their absence from the AWC due to participation in mandatory ICDS trainings and meetings, as neglect of their responsibilities (Lall et al., 2024)

Enrollment & Average daily attendance of children

The number of children is an important factor in determining the quality of education in an educational institution.

Figure 4: Enrollment & Average daily attendance of children

ANOVA tests indicate statistically significant differences in average attendance across the frequency of No of children. (F-statistic ≈ 37.5 , $p < 0.001$). This confirms attendance varies meaningfully between different frequencies of No of children. Across all frequencies of No of children, enrollment numbers are generally higher than average attendance in a day. This indicates that while children are enrolled in school, not all of them attend regularly. For a higher frequency, the number of children enrolled decreases substantially but still exceeds attendance, confirming attendance drop-off.

Pearson Correlation (linear relationship) analysis shows a strong positive relationship between enrollment and attendance (Pearson correlation ≈ 0.98), signifying that attendance largely depends on enrollment, but other factors cause gaps. The trend also shows attendance declines faster than enrollment as the frequency of children increases. The analysis highlights a finding that enrollment alone does not guarantee regular attendance, which in turn suggests the need for policies and interventions focusing not just on enrollment but also on supporting consistent daily attendance. In the survey, AWWs opined that in AWCs, enrollment differs from the average attendance of children mainly due to the parents' attitude. They are not giving importance to the regular attendance of children in AWCs. The National Family Health Survey-5 (NFHS-5) reveals that just 13.6% of children are enrolled in pre-primary schools.

Theme-based education

The Women and Child Development Department, Government of Kerala, introduced theme-based education in 2014. The Department has developed the 'Ankanapoomazha'-workbook for children and the 'Ankanathaimavu'-activity-based guidebook for AWWs for the Theme-based education.

The study found that all AWWs follow theme-based education. However, they suggested the content should be lessened according to the age level of children. Because usually

children of 3-4 years of age are attending AWCs. Thereafter, parents send the children to KGs. From the viewpoint of AWWs, some songs are lengthy, and activities are hard for this age group. Children in this age group grasp rhymes with 4 or 5 lines and like to do activities through the play way method rather than merely sitting and doing. Centre for Early Childhood Education and Development (CECED,2012) supervised some studies that have viewed ECE programs around the country, revealing a predominance of academic instruction being conveyed at this stage, which indicates a downward extension of the primary curriculum; this will not be favourable for children since they are not mature enough for the curriculum.

The availability of time to follow the Ankanawadi curriculum from the viewpoint of the selected aWWs.

Non-formal Preschool education is an important service provided through AWCs. In Kerala, the Women and Child Development Department has developed two books, namely 'Ankanathaimav' and 'Ankanapoomazha', for nonformal preschool education. It consists of 30 themes, where two activities are held per month and six special themes are based on different festivals or national celebrations. Each theme offers five different activities every day. It covers five developmental domains- Language Development, Physical Development, Socio-emotional Development, Creative Development and Cognitive Development.

The AWWs have other duties than an early childhood educator as they need to accomplish all six objectives of ICDS. Sometimes they also have to give details to higher officials, meetings by the mother Department and other Departments during pre-school time, election duties, etc. So it affects the time for pre-school education.

Figure 5: The availability of time to follow the Ankanawadi curriculum

Figure 5 shows that 69 per cent of AWWs did not get enough time to follow the Ankanawadi curriculum. One-third of the AWWs are feeling burdened due to their

participation in national health initiatives and election responsibilities, on top of their usual duties (Desai G & Pandit N, 2012). Research into the time management and work challenges of AWWs has revealed that they can only allocate 54 per cent of their time to essential duties such as preschool education and home visits. They face a significant burden of record-keeping. (Joshi K, 2018). In Kerala, AWWs have to maintain 11 records, namely family survey book, food stock register, supplementary nutrition food supply, pre-school education, pregnant women and lactating mothers, immunisation, vitamins, growth monitoring, house visit, referral services and conclusion. They also need to maintain a daily diary, an asset register, minutes of ALMSC meeting, adolescent girls meeting, meeting of parents for class regarding ECCE, Community Based Event meeting (CBE), in addition to all these registers.

It is also affected by children's time to adapt to the environment of AWCs, the attention span of children, their age level, and their activities in between activities like talking to each other, self-talk, fighting, hugging, etc. So AWWs were not able to do the activities in the 'ankanathaimav' as directed by the authorities. The rest of AWWs (31%) stated that they had the time to follow the curriculum. However, the majority of them focused on ECE by doing other duties when the children were asleep, after the working hours of AWCs, or even from home. So it is clear that AWWs have less time to follow the prescribed Ankanwadi curriculum than expected due to the time constraints. On average, Anganwadi Workers dedicated 95 minutes per day to preschool activities, which is falling short of the expected daily requirement by 25 minutes (Jain, A et al., 2020).

Concept of AWWs about AWC as an early learning centre and performance as an early childhood educator

The WCD of Kerala is providing theme-based education through AWCs by considering the importance of AWCs as an early learning centre. Theme-based education ensures all domains of development during the early years.

Chi-Square Test for Independence was used to determine whether there is a significant association between two categorical variables, such as concepts about AWC as an early learning centre and AWWs' perception about their performance as an early educator. Null Hypothesis (H₀) was there is no association between the concept and the type of response. The distribution of positive and negative responses is the same for both concepts. Alternative Hypothesis (H₁) was there is an association between the concept and the type of response. The distribution of positive and negative responses differs between the two concepts. From the observed and expected values, the Chi-Square statistic was calculated to be approximately

11.32, and the p-value is approximately 0.00076. The p-value (0.00076) is much less than the common significance level of 0.05. This means we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant association between the concept and response type. The way AWWs respond towards the two concepts differs significantly. This difference in responses indicates that the AWWs consider AWCs as early learning centres; they feel less confident about themselves as good early childhood educators.

The AWWs follow theme-based education and perceive AWC as an early learning centre, yet many are unsure about their duty as early childhood educators. It was determined that AWWs generally have an average awareness of non-formal preschool education, highlighting the need for consistent, high-quality training and on-site instruction. Despite having worked at AWCs for 11-15 years, their skills remain underdeveloped, resulting in an average level of knowledge (Arya and Vig, 2023).

CONCLUSION

In Kerala, there has been an expansion in the number of AWCs, but there is insufficient focus on the quality of early childhood education. Because a considerable portion of AWWs' time is allocated to administrative duties, which detracts from their ability to provide early childhood education. Addressing the issues in implementation could empower the ICDS to achieve marked outcomes in early childhood education, which attracts more children to AWCs. It will ensure universal access to high-quality Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) throughout the country by 2030, which is the primary objective of NEP 2020.

REFERENCES

- Arya, M., & Vig, D. (2022). Knowledge level of Anganwadi workers about non-formal preschool education of Integrated Child Development Services. *Journal of Krishi Vigyan*, 11, 239–244. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2349-4433.2022.00138.6>
- Arya, M., & Vig, D. (2023). Impact of Anganwadi workers' soft skills on Anganwadi children's developmental milestones. *Indian Journal of Extension Education*, 59(3), 118–121.
- Das, R., & Bhattacharjee, P. (2015). A study on utilization of ICDS scheme among children below 6 years age in an urban area of Agartala, Tripura. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 5, 494–496.
- Desai, G., & Pandit, N. (2012). Changing role of Anganwadi workers: A study conducted in Vadodara district. *Healthline*, 41(4).
- International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) and ICF. (2021). *National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–21: India*. IIPS and ICF. <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/FR375/FR375.pdf>
- Jain, A., Walker, D. M., Avula, R., Diamond-Smith, N., Gopalakrishnan, L., Menon, P., ... & Fernald, L. C. (2020). Anganwadi worker time use in Madhya Pradesh, India: A cross-sectional study. *BMC Health Services Research*, 20(1), 1130. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-020-05923-9>
- Joshi, K. (2018). Knowledge of Anganwadi workers and their problems in rural ICDS block. *IP Journal of Paediatric Nursing Science*, 1, 8–14.

Lall, G., Roy, R., Chandrika, K. S., & Divan, G. (2024). "The early years are like a foundation for the future": Perspectives, facilitators, and challenges of Anganwadi workers in supporting early child development interventions in Hyderabad, India: Qualitative findings from a scalable program incorporating early child development interventions. *Indian Journal of Public Health*, 68(2), 214–221. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijph.ijph_868_23

Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India. (2020). *National Education Policy 2020* (pp. 7–8).